

SPES Focus - Work Package #6

Review of the most likely risks and shocks in Europe

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Disclaimer

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Abstract

This report provides a systematic review of the most likely risks and shocks in Europe. The analysis focuses on medium-term risks expected in the next 5-10 years, harmonizing findings from various reports. We use thematic and content analysis to identify recurring patterns, grouping risks into 15 unified concepts. Risks are categorized based on the frequency of mention, with more frequently cited risks considered more significant. The methodology ensures comparability despite differing frameworks and terminologies in the reports. Climate change, geopolitics, and biodiversity consistently rank as top concerns across global and European contexts. It is also noteworthy that many risks are interconnected. To better understand the intertwined risks, we focus on climate change, which stands out as a critical concern. Besides highlighting the more direct negative consequences, we showcase the complex and widespread effects across multiple areas.

1. Context

In recent years the global landscape has witnessed a series of significant events, including the COVID-19 pandemic, the return of war in Europe, the renewed tension in the Middle East or between US and China. There have also been escalating climate change-induced extreme weather events, alongside rapid advancements in artificial intelligence (AI), exemplified by platforms like ChatGPT. The emerging risks associated with all these developments are challenging to perceive and quantify due to their long-term consequences and uncertain evolution.

Shedding some light, international organizations, global think-tanks, and insurance and private companies have taken the lead and published several reports addressing some associated risks. Given the unpredictability of future shocks, most of these reports rely on experts' opinions, although some carry out public opinion polls or combine risk experts' knowledge with survey-based opinions. Focusing on Europe, the European Parliament started monitoring future shocks, focusing on specific risks and assessing the capabilities and resilience of the EU system in addressing multiple challenges. The report highlights 15 risks related to geopolitics, climate change, health, economics and democracy that could occur in the coming decade. Although each risk has its specific characteristics and potential impact, the report recognizes the cross-sectoral, trans-geographical and global nature of the challenges to come. The report emphasizes two key concepts: "polycrises", this is, the risk of intertwined crises, and "permacrisis", when different types of crises not only coincide in time but also persist through time (EPRS-IPOL-EXPO, 2023).

The Chatham House, the Royal Institute of International Affairs, also stresses the importance of tipping points and cascading risks given their potential to have even more devastating consequences for people and societies (Quiggin et al., 2021). The world is, indeed, characterized by highly complex and intertwined risks. Considering the different dimensions and interconnections between risks, here we overview the most expected risks in the medium-long run, as they have the potential to cause substantial socioeconomic shocks.

This evolving risk landscape presents a complex puzzle for policymakers, who must address both urgent short-term crises and long-term challenges, while also responding to societal concerns and growing uncertainty. In response, four Horizon Europe research and innovation projects – SPES, ToBe, WISE Horizons, and WISER – have proposed a European policy agenda to tackle these multifaceted challenges (Hoekstra et al., 2024). This report aims to broaden the understanding of such uncertainties and contribute to informed policy development withing the SPES framework (Biggeri et al., 2023).

The remaining of the report is organized as follows: the second section describes the reports considered under the systematic review, additionally explaining the steps we have followed to identify recurring patterns and group the risks. The third section presents the most likely risks, discussing its implications and the intertwined nature of risk, putting particular emphasis on climate change. The fourth section concludes.

2. Systematic Review

We have selected eight recent reports published by international institutions, governing bodies, insurance, and consultancy companies to get a comprehensive picture. Given the importance of “polycrises” and the global nature of many risks, we have focused on general risk-assessment reports rather than on sectorial ones, such as food or energy specific documents. Inevitably, some reports are more oriented towards a specific area like geopolitics, security or climate, but despite exploring the matter through those lenses, we ensured that they are all broad enough to provide a general overview (see the list of reports and main characteristics on Appendix I).¹

Three quarters of the reports present a global perspective, with a few also incorporating a regional analysis and a couple exclusively analysing Europe. This regional view will be particularly useful to discuss mid-term future European challenges and threats. The risk classifications and time dimensions also vary from one report to another. Some explore a particular time span, while others include current crises and separately identify the risks foreseen for the next 5 years and for longer periods (over 10 years). Similarly, some reports present a list of the most concerning risks, sometimes being ranked by importance, whereas others group risks into high/medium/low risks or high/active/initial concerns based on specific criteria.

Going beyond the specific framing employed in each report while ensuring comparability, we focus on medium-term risks, those expected in the next 5-10 years and beyond and select the most severe risks from each report. On average, we get a list of 10 risks per report. As similar risks are differently named or described in each report, we follow the literature on content and thematic analysis to define a coherent and harmonized list of risks (Nowell et al, 2017; Krippendorff, 2018). Both approaches search for patterns and themes across data, but their main difference is that content analysis quantifies data by measuring the frequency of categories and themes, which can serve as a proxy for significance (Vaismoradi, Turunen, H., and Bondas, 2013). Overall, thematic analysis focuses on extracting high-level themes from within data, while content analysis focuses on the reoccurrence of concepts or keywords at a more surface-level of analysis.

Based on the traditional thematic analysis, we started examining the reports to identify common themes, risks, patterns of meaning that come up recurrently. We then determined the presence of these concepts as done in content analysis. This is basically a process of selective reduction. After familiarizing ourselves with the list of risks derived from the reports, we created a code or keywords that describes their content. We then identified patterns among the codes and defined the broader themes. We end up having fifteen concepts, each one expressing a different and often cited risk. The Appendix II summarizes the 15 concepts, the associated key words and their description.

We finally grouped the original list of risks coming from the reports, which present different names and descriptions, into one of the 15 concepts if they include any of the words defined in the “code”. For instance, we have created a concept called migration, whose code includes the following words: migration and displacement. Then, we go to the list of risks derived from the reports and check which one includes any of those words. In this case, the following risks would fall under the “migration” category: migration pressure, weaponization of irregular migration, and involuntary migration.

Once we have the unified list of concepts, we detected the most mentioned risks by counting how many times each concept appears. The more times a risk is cited, the more significant or threatening we consider it to be in the medium-long term. This exercise assumes that all reports are equally

¹ We selected 12 reports, but only 8 were deemed valid. All 8 reports are listed in Appendix I, along with the reasons for dismissing the other four. To the best of our knowledge, searches in Scopus, Web of Science and Google Scholar did not yield any additional publications on global risk assessment.

important regardless of their geographic coverage, as we do not distinguish if the risk is identified globally or for Europe. Given our interest in Europe, we designed a weighting scheme to account for this matter. When counting the risks, those listed in reports with a European focus count one, while we assign a value of 0.5 to the rest.

3. Risks and Cascading Effects

As shown in Table 1, both approaches deliver a similar ranking of risks. Climate change, geopolitics and biodiversity/ecosystems consistently appear as top concerns in both global and European contexts. These three subjects remain at the top when we take the order of importance or severity into account.²

Appendix II helps to understand which are the most cited risks, they are presented in order of importance, and what they entail. However, we now look closer to the shocks that the top 3 risks could imply in Europe. Among all the possible climate related shocks and its adverse effects, warming will impact the EU agricultural sector via wildfires and droughts. While water and heat stresses have already reduced crop yields, future projection estimate that net yield losses will reduce economic output from agriculture by 7% in the EU, and 10% in Southern Europe at a +4°C scenario (Naumann et al., 2021). Southern Europe will indeed face higher damages to the agricultural system, affecting not only the food availability and prices for European households, but also altering local employment markets. This is especially concerning since Southern Europe has been highlighted as a drought hot spot in the European Drought Risk Atlas (Rossi et al., 2023).

² Although some reports just provide a list of top risks or high/medium/low risk classifications, others build rankings. To exploit this dual information, we selected those reports providing a ranking (all provide a list of 10 risk) and created an alternative weighting scheme (ranging from 1 to 0.1). Thus, we consider the relative importance and urgency of each risk when counting the risks named in those reports. Results are available upon request.

Table 1. Ranking of risk: Global vs. European Focus

	Global		Europe
Climate change	10	Biodiversity/ecosystem/natural resources	6.5
Geopolitics	10	Geopolitics	6.5
Biodiversity/ecosystem/natural resources	8	Climate change	6
Health	8	Health	5.5
Artificial Intelligence	6	Financial / debt crisis	4.5
Food and water	6	Food and water	4
Infrastructures/supply chains	5	Artificial Intelligence	3.5
Financial/debt crisis	5	Infrastructures/supply chains	3.5
Growth/inflation	5	Growth/inflation	3.5
Internet	4	Internet	3
Migration	3	Social tension	2.5
Social tension	3	Energy	2.5
Energy	3	Migration	2
Information	2	Information	1.5
Demographics	2	Demographics	1.5

Source: Own elaboration.

River flood risk is also projected to rise across Europe, while coastal floods will dramatically increase along most coastlines due to accelerating sea level rise. Critical infrastructures near rivers and seas will face higher risk of damage and disruption. With 3°C global warming, economic damages caused by floods would be six times larger by 2100, reaching €48 billion/year, and nearly half a million people would be affected in the EU and UK (Feyen et al., 2020).

As reviewed by Bednar-Friedl et al. (2022), biodiversity has deteriorated both globally and in Europe. Unsustainable exploitation of natural resources is causing biodiversity to decline at an unprecedented rate in human history, jeopardizing both present and future well-being. Biodiversity plays a critical role in providing essential services to humanity, not only by providing food, feed, timber, bioenergy and other materials, but also through its regulatory services, which balance climate, air and water quality (IPBES, 2018; Díaz et al, 2019). Beyond the impact on food security, biodiversity loss can have significant economic costs, impacting sectors that depend on healthy ecosystems such as agriculture, fisheries and tourism. From a health perspective, it can also increase the risk of zoonotic diseases and reduce resilience to epidemics and pandemics, risking human health. Moreover, many medicines are derived from natural sources and biodiversity loss

reduces the potential for discovering new treatments. Given the continuous strong decline of biodiversity, European countries are exposed to these variety of shocks.

Regarding geopolitics, global conflicts have devastating socioeconomic consequences, but tensions with Russia have become one of the key geopolitical challenges in Europe. In addition to the invasion of Ukraine, Russia has recently escalated its use of hybrid destabilization tactics (European Union Institute for Security Studies, 2020). The economic and energy interdependencies with Russia additionally pose significant threats to the EU, such as decreased trade, shortages of raw materials, inflationary pressures and rising defence expenditures.

In response to these challenges and being concerned about energy security, the EU has been reducing its reliance on Russian fossil fuels and endorsing green initiatives. However, Europe's high dependence on critical raw materials could hinder the green and digital transitions and undermine efforts to achieve strategic autonomy. Conflicts in other territories, such as the China-Taiwan tension, could have profound ramifications for the EU. The scarcity of semiconductor chips would be particularly acute, disrupting entire value chains across various industries, both in Europe and abroad (EPRS-IPOL-EXPO, 2023). The repercussions would extend beyond the economic sphere, potentially fuelling growing social unrest within EU Member States. The sharp rise in consumer prices, especially in energy, would additionally diminish societal well-being.

While the above-mentioned shocks threaten the EU, the diversity of economic sectors and climate makes European regions unequally exposed and vulnerable to these shocks. Although climate change damages economies and the welfare of households in the continent, a north-south divide has been identified in the regional distribution of welfare losses. The sum of climate related impacts in northern regions are relatively small or even positive, due to an increasing agricultural and energy production, whereas the impacts are mostly negative in southern Europe (Feyen et al., 2020). Identifying these regional differences is also necessary for an adequate implementation of mitigation and adaptation policies.

We do not conduct this in-depth analysis for the remaining risks, but Appendix II provides a general description of each risk and its associated threats. Despite providing a broad picture and not delving into the details and underlying mechanisms, it is noteworthy that many risks are interconnected. Townend, Aylett and Benzie (2023) have already explored the overarching impact of cascading climate risks, showing how different types of climate triggers and transmission mechanisms can affect European societies.

To better understand the intertwined risks, we focus on climate change, which stands out as a critical concern. Both climate change and biodiversity/ecosystems, which can be encompassed within the former category, are in the top of our ranking. In fact, most of the reports previously reviewed agree that climate and environmental risks will dominate over the next decades. For example, AXA has tracked for a decade the changing perceptions regarding the vulnerabilities to which our societies are exposed. Notably, climate change has recently gained unanimous recognition as the main risk (AXA, 2023).

Based on the reviewed reports, we created a graph illustrating how climate change affects different dimensions, each one being represented by a colour, and its potential cascading consequences due to the interconnections between these sectors, as exemplified by the coloured arrows. Central to the diagram is the concept of climate hazards, which include increasing temperatures, changing precipitation patterns and more severe weather events, such as heatwaves, droughts and floodings. These climate hazards significantly affect ecosystems by causing biodiversity loss, natural degradation and coastal erosion. Health is also compromised through increased mortality, morbidity and the spread of infectious and vector-borne diseases. The built environment suffers from damaged infrastructure and disrupted transport and storage systems, while the economy faces challenges like reduced production, more competition for resources, rising costs and threats to social justice. Additionally, lower water availability and quality risks water security, in turn affecting food production and availability, which is also affected by wildfires and other climate shocks. Energy systems are also disrupted, facing challenges to meet the increasing demand.

Besides highlighting the more direct negative consequences of climate change, the graph emphasizes the interconnected nature of these impacts, showcasing the complex and widespread effects across multiple areas. The arrows underscore the intricate web of interdependencies, revealing how the effects in one sector can ripple through and amplify challenges in others. For instance, ecosystem degradation can lead to biological invasions, threatening human health by increasing infectious diseases. It can also affect soil and food dynamics, while a shortage of natural resources may reduce both energy and overall economic production. Changes in rainfall patterns and water scarcity also affect agriculture, with the potential to worsen nutrient security, mortality and morbidity levels, which in turn pressures the health system and increases economic costs.

Although climate shocks occurring in a specific area, such as floods or wildfires, only destroy local infrastructure and buildings, their effects can spread over the globe, for instance, if supply chains are interrupted. The 2021 crash of the *Evergreen*, a colossal container ship, in the Suez Canal highlighted this issue. The incident questioned supply chains' resilience and the strength of just-in-time manufacturing, which were already facing shortages due to the COVID-19 pandemic. Similarly, drought-induced crop failure in agriculture intensive regions could lead to global food inflation, affecting food insecurity and social welfare. This adverse effect could be reinforced if co-occurring conflict in other places disrupts food distribution systems.

In a globalized economy, shocks emerging in remote locations can indeed have far-reaching impacts on societies and economies elsewhere due to interconnected transmission systems. In this regard, Carter et al. (2021) have created a framework to understand cross-border climate change impacts, highlighting the importance of global dynamics. Aware of this situation, the EU is actively strategizing to address this multifaceted challenge. The revised EU Strategy on Adaptation to Climate Change in 2021 (EC, 2021) acknowledges the transboundary nature of climate hazards' spillover effects and emphasizes that effective adaptation must transcend borders.

4. Conclusions

This report presents a systematic review of the most significant risks and shocks expected in Europe over the medium term, spanning the next 5 to 10 years. By synthesizing insights from the literature, the analysis employs thematic and content analysis to identify recurring patterns, consolidating these into 15 unified risk categories. The risks are ranked by the frequency of their mention, with those cited most often deemed the most critical. A weighting system emphasizes European-focused risks, assigning them higher importance. This methodology facilitates comparability across diverse frameworks and terminologies used in the reviewed reports.

Key concerns consistently highlighted across both global and European contexts include climate change, geopolitical tensions, and biodiversity loss. While the implications and ramifications of these three risks are discussed in the text, the implications of the remaining twelve risks are broadly described in Appendix II. Importantly, we find that many risks are deeply interconnected, which highlights the importance of accounting for cascading effects.

We take climate change as a case study to better understand the intertwined risks. Beyond examining its direct negative consequences, our analysis highlights the intricate and far-reaching impacts across multiple domains. These connections not only call for a comprehensive global risk assessment, including cascading effects, but also underscore the pressing need for holistic mitigation and adaptation strategies to tackle these multifaceted challenges effectively. In doing so, this report stressed the importance of the recently published “A European Agenda to Navigate Uncertain Times. How to Steer the EU Towards Wellbeing for All, Now and in the Future” (Hoekstra et al., 2024) and the SPES framework (Biggeri et al., 2023).

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Annex I: Review of reports

INSTITUTION	REPORT TITLE	PUBLICATION	METHODOLOGY	PERSPECTIVE	TIME SPAN	SEVERITY	FOCUS
The World Economic Forum (WEF)	The global risks report 2024 – 19th edition	2024	Survey experts	Global	1-,2- and 10-year horizons	Ranking of risks	General
AXA	Future Risks Report 2023	2023	Survey experts and general population	Global and continental	Next 5-10 years	Ranking of risks	General
Generali	Emerging and sustainability risks booklet 2023	2023	Internal group assessment and literature review	Global	10 years	Risks grouped: high, active and initial concern	General
European CRO Forum	Emerging Risk Initiative - Major Trends and Emerging Risk Radar 2023	2023	Experts' assessment and survey amongst Forum members	Global	Next 5 years and beyond	Risks grouped: high, medium and low impact	Insurance
European Parliamentary Research Service, the Directorates-General for Internal Policies and External Policies (EPRS – IPOL-EXPO)	Future Shocks 2023 Anticipating and weathering the next storms	2023	Literature review	Europe	Next 5-10 years	None	General

Chatam House, the Royal Institute of International Affairs	Climate change risk assessment 2021	2021	Experts' assesment; elicitation exercise	Global	Next 20-30 years	None	Climate
International military council on climate and security (IMCCS)	The world climate and security report 2021	2021	Survey experts	Global	Today, 10- and 20- year horizons	Ranking of risks	Climate
European Environmental Agency (EEA)	European Climate Risk Assessment Report	2024	Experts', policymakers' and stakeholders' assessment	Europe	current (2021-2040), mid-century (2041-2060) late century (2081-2100)	Riks grouped based on the urgency to act (5 classes) and risk severity (4 classes)	Climate

EXCLUDED REPORTS			
INSTITUTION	REPORT TITLE	PUBLICATION	REASON EXCLUDED
OECD	2022 Risks that Matter Survey	2023	Survey working-age respondents on the socioeconomic risks they face. Individual focus, not global.
Eurasia Group	Top Risks 2024 for Europe		Risk in the current year, not useful for future evaluations.
AXA	Foresight report 2024: 100 reasons to love the future	2024	Focuses on the reasons to love the future, does not assess risks.
Economist Intelligence Unit (EUI)	Top global risk scenarios	2023	Current and next 2 years risks, not useful for future evaluations.

Annex II: Review of risk: concept, key words and description

CONCEPT	CODE	DESCRIPTION
Climate change	Extreme weather event, climate change, natural disaster, flood, heat	Climate change presents a constellation of risks, primarily driven by human-induced global warming. This includes heightened occurrences of extreme weather events such as wildfires, floods, hurricanes, heatwaves and other temperature-related extremes, resulting in significant loss of life, property damage, financial losses and ecosystem destruction. Additionally, climate tipping points pose long-term, potentially irreversible, changes to critical Earth systems, like sea level rise from melting ice sheets and carbon release from thawing permafrost, further exacerbating global impacts. Pollution from human activities, affecting air, soil, and water quality, compounds these major risks, leading to health impacts, economic losses and environmental degradation.
Geopolitics	Geopolitical instability, tension, conflict, destabilization, national-military-international security, transatlantic relations, presidency,	Geopolitical risks encompass a spectrum of threats stemming from interactions between nations and global dynamics. For instance, the US-China tensions have sparked a trade war involving tariffs and technology restrictions, disrupting global supply chains and economic stability. The conflict in Ukraine demonstrates how military tensions can escalate, impacting European security and triggering humanitarian crises. Regional disputes such as those between Serbia and Kosovo, and ongoing conflicts in the Middle East and Africa, contribute to instability and violence. Economic shifts, such as challenges to the petrodollar system and the rise of BRICS economies, highlight new geopolitical pressures. Military advancements, including cyber warfare capabilities, add complexities to international relations. Environmental factors like climate change

	China-Taiwan, Russia-Ukraine	exacerbate social inequalities and could lead to mass migrations, straining governance structures globally.
Biodiversity Ecosystem Natural resources	Biodiversity, ecosystem, natural resource, ecosystem	The convergence of various environmental risks poses significant challenges to biodiversity, ecosystems and human well-being globally. Biodiversity loss and ecosystem collapse threaten the natural capital essential for sustaining life and economic activities on Earth. Cascading risks, triggered by climate-driven shifts in weather patterns and ecosystem dynamics, further amplify vulnerabilities, leading to potential crop failures, food insecurity and population displacement. These environmental pressures stem from direct factors such as overexploitation of land and species or pollution, as well as indirect drivers including population growth, economic development and urbanization. Overall, these interconnected environmental risks underscore the urgency of comprehensive global efforts to mitigate climate change, conserve biodiversity, and ensure sustainable management of natural resources to safeguard human security and resilience in the face of escalating environmental threats.
Health	Pandemics, antimicrobial resistance, medical advances, health, heat stress	Health risks encompass potential threats to individual and public health originating from various sources. It includes the escalation of pandemics and antimicrobial resistance (AMR), which diminish the effectiveness of medical treatments and pose substantial challenges to global healthcare systems. Climate change further amplifies health risks by exacerbating heat stress, air pollution and the geographic spread of vector-borne diseases like those carried by mosquitoes. These environmental changes not only increase mortality and morbidity rates but also strain healthcare infrastructure and pose specific risks to outdoor workers.

<p>Artificial Intelligence (AI)</p>	<p>Artificial intelligence, big data, digitalization, smart automation, autonomous machines</p>	<p>Key risks associated with AI and big data involve disruptive technologies affecting individuals, businesses, ecosystems and economies. Beyond the risk of cyberattacks aimed at financial gain, espionage or sabotage, digitalization can amplify disinformation and election interference. There are also tech-related economic risks, such as those linked to cryptocurrencies and fintech. From a work perspective, automation raises issues of labor substitution and unemployment, increasing social tensions. It also exacerbates the already observed digital gap, calling for reskilling and upskilling policies. The lack of transparency and human oversight in AI decision-making also poses ethical concerns. For instance, autonomous machines introduce accountability questions in the event of accidents. Additionally, regulatory gaps in AI governance could undermine European competitiveness in this rapidly evolving field.</p>
<p>Food and water</p>	<p>Food, water, crop, drought</p>	<p>Food and water security face escalating threats from climate change, with hydrological droughts emerging as major global risk, provoking economic losses, water shortages and humanitarian crises. These droughts have intensified, affecting regions such as Mali, Niger, Burkina Faso, the US and China. By 2040, nearly 700 million people are expected to annually endure prolonged droughts, doubling the historical average. Extreme weather events like heatwaves and floods disrupt agriculture, reduce crop yields and destabilize global food markets, causing price spikes and socio-economic unrest. Rising sea levels further exacerbate coastal water insecurity through saltwater intrusion and flooding, particularly impacting vulnerable communities. Climate-induced shifts in precipitation patterns also worsen freshwater scarcity, affecting agriculture and increasing socio-economic tensions.</p>

<p>Infrastructures Supply chains</p>	<p>Infrastructure, supply chain, raw material, building</p>	<p>Failures in both critical infrastructure and supply chain pose significant risks to governments, businesses and individuals. Critical infrastructure failures can severely disrupt essential services such as electricity provision, water supply and communications and transport infrastructure. These disruptions are often caused by chronic underinvestment in physical infrastructure, but climate change can further exacerbate it. Beyond the immediate physical damage to infrastructure and buildings, which incurs direct economic costs, these failures can also disrupt key sectors and trade routes, significantly amplifying indirect costs. Geopolitical tensions also threaten global trade and critical supply chains, particularly for essential raw materials like semiconductors. The EU's heavy reliance on imports for raw materials amplifies these vulnerabilities, potentially hampering the EU's decarbonization goals and industrial development. Overall, these threats could lead to shortages, interruptions and significant economic losses, undermining stability and growth.</p>
<p>Growth Inflation</p>	<p>Macroeconomic risk, prices, growth, trade disruption, economic security, market</p>	<p>There are different macroeconomic risks that threaten economic growth and stability. Climatic shocks are of particular concern because of their potential to impact food security, energy and water infrastructure, as well as to cause business defaults. Relatedly, supply chain disruptions, inflation, sovereign debt defaults, unemployment and economic insecurity all become major threats. Globalization poses further challenges. A significant deceleration in China's medium-term growth could adversely impact the EU, not only through direct trade channels, but also via a decelerating spillover effect on neighboring countries. The emergence of new competitors in different markets, such as FinTech and InsurTech, could also diminish the EU's market and political influence. If these adverse effects disproportionately affect marginalized and poorer communities, economic and social inequality could also increase.</p>

Financial crisis Debt crisis	Financial stability, debt, fintech, solidarity	<p>Financial risks encompass the potential for significant financial losses or instability due to factors such as high debt levels, economic downturns, market volatility and geopolitical crises. These risks include bankruptcies, liquidity crises and defaults, including sovereign debt, with all being exacerbated by rising interest rates and inflation. The financial system also faces challenges from the physical impacts of climate change, which strain public finances and increasing insurance costs. These effects disproportionately affect vulnerable groups, which may interact with other non-climatic risks like pandemics and geopolitical tensions.</p>
Internet	Internet, cyber insecurity, cyber risk	<p>Risks related to the internet encompass a broad spectrum of threats, including cyberwarfare, cyberespionage and cybercrime, aimed at gaining digital control or disrupting operations. These risks are exacerbated by geopolitical tensions, technological advancements such as quantum computing and artificial intelligence, and the evolving attack surface. Potential consequences range from financial and operational losses due to business interruption and data breaches to broader societal impacts like internet fragmentation and compromised critical infrastructure.</p>
Migration	Migration, displacement	<p>The main risk is related to involuntary and irregular migration. Key drivers include lack of economic opportunities, human-made and natural disasters, climate change and conflicts. Regardless of the cause, migration poses challenges to Europe. The Middle East conflict outstands for its potential contribution to inflation, via oil prices, and migratory pressures, both affecting Europe. The weaponization of irregular migration by governments also emerges as a tool to destabilize regions. Finally, climate risks further drive displacement and migration pressures, leading to socio-economic and political instability.</p>

Social tension	Social tension, social polarization, social instability, anti-establishment	<p>Social tension risks are exacerbated by factors such as economic disparities, misinformation, political polarization and external shocks like energy price crises. These tensions lead to widespread societal discontent expressed through protests and movements, challenging perceived unjust government responses and economic policies. Misinformation amplifies polarization by influencing societies to embrace biased information over factual accuracy, undermining social cohesion and trust in institutions. Persistent economic challenges, including energy price shocks, deepening inequalities, intensifying social unrest and fracturing communities. Insufficient preparedness by public authorities to address these multifaceted issues exacerbates the risk, potentially destabilizing democratic institutions and hindering efforts to find collective solutions to societal problems.</p>
Energy	Energy - risk, -supply, -security	<p>The energy-related risk has many faces. These include geopolitical concerns and the need for a transition to low-carbon energy sources due to climate change. As a major importer of energy and food, Europe is exposed to energy price shocks and supply chain vulnerabilities, which can lead to prolonged inflation and put pressure on a tight labor market. Energy security remains a challenge for the EU, with potential gas shortages due to reduced Russian imports and other global demands.</p>
Information	Information, misinformation, disinformation, election interference	<p>The risks falling under information highlight the pervasive issue of misinformation and disinformation, which significantly impact public trust and democracy. Persistent false information spread through media networks undermines trust in facts and authority, algorithm-driven polarization being a systemic threat. The risks of amplified disinformation and election interference are particularly important for Europe, where geostrategic threats like foreign information manipulation are a reality.</p>

Demographics	Demographics, demography	Demographic risks encompass population changes driven by births, deaths and migration patterns, especially notable in developed countries where ageing populations are increasing due to higher life expectancy and declining fertility rates. This shift strains the workforce as it needs to balance care for the elderly and youth. Economic challenges also arise, worsened by inflation and high commodity prices, impacting younger generations' financial security. Unexpected events like climate change can further accelerate demographic shifts, migrations and socioeconomic disruptions.
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